

Analytical Report

Sample data report

New Mexico Bureau of Geology
and Mineral Resources

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(575) 835-5160
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Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3180	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	152	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.00	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	441	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.37	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
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Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.378	mg/L	10	0.005	(0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01	(0.1)	5/18/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.168	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.68	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Chloride	639	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/11/2020
Fluoride	1.35	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Nitrate	1.03	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/11/2020
Sulfate	655	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/11/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	155	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	189	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	34.88	meq/L	1		
Cations total	33.83	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.53	%	1		
SiO2	20.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2110	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-01	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	708	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3190	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	161	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.06	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	442	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.378	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.168	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.73	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/11/2020
Fluoride	1.39	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Nitrate	0.66	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/11/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/11/2020
Sulfate	651	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	178	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	217	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.14	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.33	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.17	%	1		
SiO2	20.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2120	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-02	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	731	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3200	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	167	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.97	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	440	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.373	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.167	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.58	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	643	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.36	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	0.80	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	661	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	190	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	228	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.80	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.63	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.67	%	1		
SiO2	20.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-03	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	751	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3120	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	163	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	78.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.97	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	436	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.375	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.169	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.59	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.55	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	640	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.44	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	0.94	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	190	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	228	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

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Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.64	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.00	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.34	%	1		
SiO2	20.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-04	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	729	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3200	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	167	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	18.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.83	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	438	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.378	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.168	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.41	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.51	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0051	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	636	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.44	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	0.65	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	196	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	231	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.58	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.42	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.65	%	1		
SiO2	20.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-05	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	744	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3220	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	167	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	80.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.79	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	437	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.377	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.170	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.59	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.58	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.45	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	0.71	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	654	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	197	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	240	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.68	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.44	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.77	%	1		
SiO2	20.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-06	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	748	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	168	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.82	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	441	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.381	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.170	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.54	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.59	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	637	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.52	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	0.62	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	652	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	199	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	239	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.63	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.63	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.42	%	1		
SiO2	20.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-07	Customer sample ID: GS7	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	748	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	169	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.77	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	439	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.45	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.380	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.167	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.44	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.60	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	634	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.51	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	0.63	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	205	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	247	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.61	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.56	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.51	%	1		
SiO2	20.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-08	Customer sample ID: GS8	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	749	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	178	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.72	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	447	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.385	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.163	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.67	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.63	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.49	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	652	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	216	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	260	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.93	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.55	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.54	%	1		
SiO2	20.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-09	Customer sample ID: GS9	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	780	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	178	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.59	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	436	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.385	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.164	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.60	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.69	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0146	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	630	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.50	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	645	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	226	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	270	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.85	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.91	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.33	%	1		
SiO2	20.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-10	Customer sample ID: GS10	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	773	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	180	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	80.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.51	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	449	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.57	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.378	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.154	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.26	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.72	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0051	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0158	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	632	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.44	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	225	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	269	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.95	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.67	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.40	%	1		
SiO2	19.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-11	Customer sample ID: GS11	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	782	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	180	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	80.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.36	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	440	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.382	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.150	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.23	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.75	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0051	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0177	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	633	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	648	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	273	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.99	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.21	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.10	%	1		
SiO2	19.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-12	Customer sample ID: GS12	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	780	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	181	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	8.47	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	445	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.53	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/18/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Boron 11	0.384	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/18/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/18/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/18/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Lithium	0.150	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Manganese	0.025	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Silicon	9.36	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/18/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Strontium	3.73	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/18/2020
Uranium	0.0051	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020
Zinc 66	0.0163	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/18/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020
Fluoride	1.57	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/12/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/12/2020
Sulfate	652	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	226	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	276	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.16	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.63	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.75	%	1		
SiO2	20.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-13	Customer sample ID: GS13	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	788	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3220	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	165	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	82.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	452	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.373	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.157	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.41	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	639	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.45	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	177	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	215	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.34	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.21	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.19	%	1		
SiO2	23.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-14	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	753	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3200	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	171	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	82.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	453	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.51	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.368	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.39	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.42	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.73	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	192	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	234	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.31	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.45	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.20	%	1		
SiO2	23.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2150	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-15	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	764	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3200	uS/cm	1		5/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	168	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	79.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.0	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	444	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.373	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.156	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	630	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.53	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.64	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	650	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	197	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	238	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.39	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.72	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.95	%	1		
SiO2	23.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2140	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-16	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	747	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	172	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	80.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	449	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.154	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	11.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.45	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	632	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.48	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.65	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	650	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	206	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	251	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.62	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.27	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.49	%	1		
SiO2	23.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-17	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	764	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	179	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.0	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	448	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.52	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.159	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.48	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	628	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.42	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.64	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	648	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	220	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	265	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.75	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.57	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.26	%	1		
SiO2	23.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-18	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	780	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	176	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.94	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	449	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.52	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.157	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	626	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.58	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.87	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	645	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	210	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	257	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.46	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.50	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.07	%	1		
SiO2	23.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2160	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-19	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	774	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	179	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	80.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.88	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	444	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	11.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	630	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.53	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.68	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	223	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	272	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.91	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.36	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.78	%	1		
SiO2	23.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-20	Customer sample ID: SSS7	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	778	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	83.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	449	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.380	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.151	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	11.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	629	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.41	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.60	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	647	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	226	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	274	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.87	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.96	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.12	%	1		
SiO2	23.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-21	Customer sample ID: SSS8	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	797	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3290	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.99	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	451	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.55	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.022	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.374	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0056	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	0.0120	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	629	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.55	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	648	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.99	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.99	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.00	%	1		
SiO2	23.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-22	Customer sample ID: SSS9	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	794	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.94	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	449	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.022	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.153	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	11.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.52	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	0.0135	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	629	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.48	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.68	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.03	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.84	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.26	%	1		
SiO2	23.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-23	Customer sample ID: SSS10	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	792	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	184	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.92	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	453	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.58	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.371	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.153	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.59	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	0.0093	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	627	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.48	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	645	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.90	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.11	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.29	%	1		
SiO2	22.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-24	Customer sample ID: SSS11	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	796	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	184	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	452	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.58	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.376	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.153	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	0.0072	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.56	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	0.0127	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	634	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.49	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.57	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	657	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.35	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.06	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.41	%	1		
SiO2	23.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2200	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-25	Customer sample ID: SSS12	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	795	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		5/8/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		5/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	5/14/2020
Magnesium	81.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Silicon	9.94	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/14/2020
Sodium	448	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	5/14/2020
Strontium	3.53	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/14/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	5/19/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	5/19/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	5/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	5/19/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	5/19/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Strontium	3.56	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	5/19/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020
Zinc 66	0.0125	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	5/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Chloride	624	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020
Fluoride	1.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrate	0.73	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	5/13/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	5/13/2020
Sulfate	642	mg/L	10	1 (10)	5/13/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	5/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200402
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 4/23/2020 2:13:32 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.77	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.76	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.02	%	1		
SiO2	23.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200402-26	Customer sample ID: SSS13	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	790	mg CaCO3/ L	1		6/2/2020